

PEER REVIEW REPORT

Peer review report for:

Viana, F. L. E., Guedes, M. do S. B., Vilela, F. T. de, Figueiredo, M. D. de, Feitosa, L. I. (2025). [Transition to circular economy in the Brazilian plastic industry supply chain](#). *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), 2025. e2024-0152. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0034-759020250405>

How to cite this peer review report:

Viana, F. L. E., Guedes, M. do S. B., Vilela, F. T. de, Figueiredo, M. D. de, Feitosa, L. I. (2025). Peer review report for: Transition to circular economy in the Brazilian plastic industry supply chain. *RAE-Revista de Administração de Empresas*, 65(4), 2025. e2024-0152. [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.15794771). <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15794771>

Disclaimer: The content of the Peer Review Report is the full copy of the reviewers' and authors' reports. Typing and punctuation errors are not edited.

Reviewers:

The first did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

The second reviewer did not authorize disclosure of their identity and peer review report.

Ely Paiva , Fundação Getulio Vargas, Escola de Administração de Empresas de São Paulo, SP, Brazil

ROUND 2

Reviewer 3 Report

Reviewer: Ely Paiva

Date review returned: 22-Oct-2024

Recommendation: Major Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

Comments to the Author

The manuscript addresses a highly relevant and contemporary topic, the transition to the circular economy (CE) in the context of the Brazilian plastic packaging industry supply chain (BPPISC). The authors employed a robust approach with a combination of systematic literature review, secondary data analysis, and semi-structured interviews, which gives greater depth and credibility to the results.

Strengths

1. *Structure and Approach:* The article presents a solid structure that effectively integrates different methods of analysis, allowing for a comprehensive view of the drivers, barriers, and initiatives related to CE. The triangulation of data collected through literature, interviews, and reports is a methodological aspect that stands out.
2. *Theoretical and practical contribution:* The results presented contribute to advances in the literature on the circular economy, especially in the context of emerging economies such as Brazil, highlighting aspects such as income inequality and infrastructural challenges.
3. *Threefold analysis of the results:* The clear separation between barriers, drivers, and initiatives is a positive point. In addition, the manuscript offers a detailed analysis of Brazil's specificities, proposing practical and theoretically grounded solutions.
4. *Relevant results:* The identification of barriers specific to the Brazilian context (e.g., inefficiency of selective collection and managerial barriers) and the proposal of opportunities, such as strengthening the National Solid Waste Policy and financial mechanisms such as cashback, enrich the discussion.
5. *International connections:* The comparison with initiatives in the European Union (EU) broadens the horizon of analysis, allowing us to explore potentially applicable solutions in Brazil. Although the manuscript presents a robust structure and a relevant topic, some methodological and analytical aspects require improvement to make the academic contribution more solid. One of the main issues is whether the research question can be answered using the proposed methodological procedures in the current version. It is not convincing to find the main barriers to the implementation of CE in Brazil in an SLR of international articles. This should be better addressed in the method, and a possible separation of the SLR from the empirical part could help with this. I also couldn't find out how the interview script was developed, whether it was derived from the literature or the SLR.

The weaknesses identified are discussed below:

1. The literature review follows a predominantly descriptive approach, where different authors and their contributions are presented in isolation, without a critical or in-depth connection. This approach creates the impression that the references have been grouped together without an effort to integrate them, making it difficult to understand how the authors of the manuscript position themselves in relation to the existing debate. A more analytical review would be advisable, highlighting convergences, gaps, and points of disagreement in the literature and how the study contributes to filling these gaps. See, for example, the last two paragraphs on page 5 and the three first on page 6.
2. The manuscript lacks a critical approach to the topic. For example, the challenges associated with implementing the circular economy in Brazil are presented without problematizing the viability of the proposed solutions or questioning the limitations of the public policies analyzed. Furthermore, there is no critical analysis of the effectiveness of current initiatives or the barriers identified in other studies, which could be explored in greater depth to enrich the discussion.
3. *Position of the Authors in the Literature Review.* There is a lack of clarity about the position of the authors of the manuscript in the academic debate. The theoretical assumptions presented are not properly connected to the empirical analysis, nor do they explain how they guided the formulation of the categories of analysis. A better articulation between the references reviewed and the objectives of the study is necessary to strengthen the cohesion between the theoretical and empirical parts of the work.

4. *Insertion of the SLR into the theoretical discussion.* The systematic literature review (SLR), presented in the empirical section, could be integrated into the main literature review. Incorporating the SLR directly into the theoretical discussion would make it possible to build a more structured basis, articulating the main assumptions and trends found in the literature with the empirical analysis. It would also bring more coherence and allow us to better explore how the theoretical findings informed the methodology and categories of analysis.
5. *Insufficient detail on the interviews.* The methodological section presents little information on how the interviews were conducted. Details such as the average length of each interview, the topics covered and the techniques used to stimulate responses from the interviewees are missing. These aspects are crucial for assessing the validity of the conclusions drawn and should be clearly presented. In addition, the interview questions should be linked to the literature review.
6. *Limited Exploration of Secondary Data.* The analysis of secondary data, although mentioned as an important part of the study, is not explored in sufficient depth. It would be relevant to describe in more detail the reports, documents and legal bases analyzed, as well as the criteria for their selection and how they were used to complement the findings of the interviews. For example, explaining how secondary data contributed to the triangulation of results would be a valuable addition.
7. *Better Connection Between Data Sources.* Although the manuscript benefits from data triangulation, the relationship between the data sources (SLR, interviews, and secondary data) is not sufficiently structured at the end, making it difficult to understand how this integration was achieved. The analysis would be more robust if it demonstrated clearly how these different sources complement each other in each step of the study, highlighting discrepancies or mutual reinforcements in the findings.

Author's Response

1) Answer to AEC

Comment: *The reviewers' comments are attached for your reference.*

The reviewers have expressed appreciation for your research topic and acknowledged the manuscript's valuable contribution to the literature on the circular economy, particularly within the context of emerging economies' plastics supply chains. While one reviewer has suggested minor revisions, the other has recommended a more substantial revision.

Given the detailed and insightful feedback provided by Reviewer 2, their suggestions may serve as a solid foundation for addressing the concerns raised by both reviewers. Specifically, Reviewer 2 has emphasized the need for a major revision to enhance the manuscript's clarity and accessibility to the journal's readership.

I encourage you to carefully consider the reviewers' comments and implement the necessary revisions to strengthen your manuscript.

Answer: *Thank you very much for giving us the opportunity to review the paper. In this revision we focused efforts completely on meeting the suggestions of the reviewer 2, In this sense, we made comments related to the improvements made. Nonetheless, it was not possible to comply with the suggestion to separate the SLR from the empirical part, as this would distort what was effectively carried out in the research, since the SLR was one of the methods that supported, in a complementary way to the other data collected (secondary data and interviews), the fulfillment of the objectives. This impossibility is duly reported in a specific comment addressed to the reviewer.*

2) Answers to reviewer 1

Comment 1: Thank you for your careful attention to the feedback provided.

Answer: Thank you for reviewing our paper and for having approved its publication.

3) Answers to reviewer 2

Comment 1: *The manuscript addresses a highly relevant and contemporary topic, the transition to the circular economy (CE) in the context of the Brazilian plastic packaging industry supply chain (BPPISC). The authors employed a robust approach with a combination of systematic literature review, secondary data analysis, and semi-structured interviews, which gives greater depth and credibility to the results.*

Strengths

1. *Structure and Approach: The article presents a solid structure that effectively integrates different methods of analysis, allowing for a comprehensive view of the drivers, barriers, and initiatives related to CE. The triangulation of data collected through literature, interviews, and reports is a methodological aspect that stands out.*
2. *Theoretical and practical contribution: The results presented contribute to advances in the literature on the circular economy, especially in the context of emerging economies such as Brazil, highlighting aspects such as income inequality and infrastructural challenges.*
3. *Threefold analysis of the results: The clear separation between barriers, drivers, and initiatives is a positive point. In addition, the manuscript offers a detailed analysis of Brazil's specificities, proposing practical and theoretically grounded solutions.*
4. *Relevant results: The identification of barriers specific to the Brazilian context (e.g., inefficiency of selective collection and managerial barriers) and the proposal of opportunities, such as strengthening the National Solid Waste Policy and financial mechanisms such as cashback, enrich the discussion.*
5. *International connections: The comparison with initiatives in the European Union (EU) broadens the horizon of analysis, allowing us to explore potentially applicable solutions in Brazil.*

Answer: Thanks a lot for reviewing our paper and for the positive aspects mentioned in this comment about it.

Comment 2: *Although the manuscript presents a robust structure and a relevant topic, some methodological and analytical aspects require improvement to make the academic contribution more solid. One of the main issues is whether the research question can be answered using the proposed methodological procedures in the current version. It is not convincing to find the main barriers to the implementation of CE in Brazil in an SLR of international articles. This should be better addressed in the method, and a possible separation of the SLR from the empirical part could help with this. I also couldn't find out how the interview script was developed, whether it was derived from the literature or the SLR. The weaknesses identified are discussed below:*

Answer: Thank you for your comment. We understand that the different steps of the methodological procedures are complementary and sufficient to answer the research question, as we presented in the two parts of the results. Unfortunately, it is not possible to separate the SLR from the empirical part, because the SLR was essential for us to comprehend the primary drivers, initiatives, barriers, and opportunities for transitioning the Brazilian plastic packaging industry supply chain to a Circular Economy model, in the same way of the secondary data (reports) and the interviews. Therefore, the act of separating the SLR from the empirical material would distort the research procedures actually used by the authors. About the SLR, although we used papers published in international journals, they included evidence from Brazil. As we cited in the methodology section, we searched the Scopus and Scielo databases, using both English and Portuguese terms.

Comment 3: *The literature review follows a predominantly descriptive approach, where different authors and their contributions are presented in isolation, without a critical or in-depth connection. This approach creates the impression that the references have been grouped together without an effort to integrate them, making it difficult to understand how the authors of the manuscript position themselves in relation to the existing debate. A more analytical review would be advisable, highlighting convergences, gaps, and points of disagreement in the literature and how the study contributes to filling these gaps. See, for example, the last two paragraphs on page 5 and the three first on page 6.*

Answer: *Thank you for your comment. We have rewritten the literature review on Circular Economy to include a critical perspective related to a decolonial critique do CE, and the geopolitical background of CE adoption in Europe. Many new references have been added.*

Comment 4: *The manuscript lacks a critical approach to the topic. For example, the challenges associated with implementing the circular economy in Brazil are presented without problematizing the viability of the proposed solutions or questioning the limitations of the public policies analyzed. Furthermore, there is no critical analysis of the effectiveness of current initiatives, or the barriers identified in other studies, which could be explored in greater depth to enrich the discussion.*

Answer: *Thank you for your comment. We have rewritten the introduction to better frame the challenges associated with implementing the circular economy in Brazil. We also added a critical tone to the literature review on circular economy, which supports the problematization of proposed solutions in the results section.*

Comment 5: *Position of the Authors in the Literature Review. There is a lack of clarity about the position of the authors of the manuscript in the academic debate. The theoretical assumptions presented are not properly connected to the empirical analysis, nor do they explain how they guided the formulation of the categories of analysis. A better articulation between the references reviewed and the objectives of the study is necessary to strengthen the cohesion between the theoretical and empirical parts of the work.*

Answer: *Thank you for your analysis. We understand that our initial position was in line with the premises of circular economy as proposed, for example, by the European Union policies and drivers. However, from your comments on the need to include critical perspectives on circular economy, our view on the topic became more complex. We understand that the changes on the literature review on circular economy have clarified our position as less adherent to the EU agenda and more emphatic on the need to explore the specificities of CE possibilities in Brazil. We also understand that the addition of critical perspectives on CE in the literature review on the issue contributes to the effort of gathering theoretical references in the literature review section for the comprehension of the topic and building analytical categories. The literature review brought to the light of our analysis the practice-based and practice-oriented perspectives on CE in Europe - once it is the region where CE has been more often implemented and researched. So, we contrast a critical literature review with an analytical model that comes from a more mainstream idea of Europe-based CE to explore the Brazilian case in its singularity.*

Comment 6: *Insertion of the SLR into the theoretical discussion. The systematic literature review (SLR), presented in the empirical section, could be integrated into the main literature review. Incorporating the SLR directly into the theoretical discussion would make it possible to build a more structured basis, articulating the main assumptions and trends found in the literature with the empirical analysis. It would also bring more coherence and allow us to better explore how the theoretical findings informed the methodology and categories of analysis.*

Answer: Thank you for the suggestion. As mentioned before, unfortunately it is not possible to separate the SLR from the empirical part and include it in the main literature review, because the SLR was essential for us to comprehend the primary drivers, initiatives, barriers, and opportunities for transitioning the Brazilian plastic packaging industry supply chain to a Circular Economy model, in the same way of the secondary data (reports) and the interviews. Therefore, the act of separating the SLR from the empirical material would distort the research procedures actually used by the authors.

Comment 7: *Insufficient detail on the interviews. The methodological section presents little information on how the interviews were conducted. Details such as the average length of each interview, the topics covered, and the techniques used to stimulate responses from the interviewees are missing. These aspects are crucial for assessing the validity of the conclusions drawn and should be clearly presented. In addition, the interview questions should be linked to the literature review.*

Answer: Thanks a lot for the comment. We have added information about the average length of interviews, as well as mentioned some techniques used to stimulate interviewees' responses in the methodology section.

Comment 8: *Limited Exploration of Secondary Data. The analysis of secondary data, although mentioned as an important part of the study, is not explored in sufficient depth. It would be relevant to describe in more detail the reports, documents and legal bases analyzed, as well as the criteria for their selection and how they were used to complement the findings of the interviews. For example, explaining how secondary data contributed to the triangulation of results would be a valuable addition.*

Answer: Thank you very much for your suggestions. We have added a paragraph to the methodology highlighting the complementary role of different sources and their adherence to the practice of data triangulation. Although we recognize the importance of secondary data in achieving the results, we explored only one excerpt from one of the reports in the results due to space limitations and because we noticed a greater wealth of detail in the interviews. The Brazilian legal framework (especially the NSWP) was explored in the discussion. The details of the types of secondary data used are presented in Table 1.

Comment 9: *Better Connection Between Data Sources. Although the manuscript benefits from data triangulation, the relationship between the data sources (SLR, interviews, and secondary data) is not sufficiently structured at the end, making it difficult to understand how this integration was achieved. The analysis would be more robust if it demonstrated clearly how these different sources complement each other in each step of the study, highlighting discrepancies or mutual reinforcements in the findings.*

Answer: Thanks a lot for your comment. In the previous version of the paper, we made an effort to describe clearly the role of each data source in the results, adding four paragraphs in the beginning of the results' section detailing the main results based on the SLR. In this new version we added a sentence in the 6th paragraph of the results that highlights that much of the evidence found in the documents and interviews was consistent with that obtained by the SLR, but there were also additional factors that deserve to be highlighted, which reinforces the role of complementarity between the different research sources.

ROUND 3

Reviewer 3 Report

Reviewer: Ely Paiva

Date review returned: 14-Mar-2025

Recommendation: Minor Revision

Please state any conflict(s) of interest that you have in relation to the review of this paper (state “none” if this is not applicable).

None

Comments to the Author

The current version has considerably improved the discussion, effectively addressing the gaps present in the first version. By incorporating a more critical perspective, it strengthens the discussion, particularly in the context of developing economies. However, there is one specific detail that, in my opinion, should be revised. In both the abstract and the method section, the authors describe the study as an exploratory case study. Given the current stage of scholarly discussion on the topic, I suggest referring to it simply as a case study.